

Control of Fusarium wilt disease of *Solanum lycopersicum* MILL. (Tomato) using *Trichoderma asperellum*

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Abstract

Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* MILL.) is a valuable crop worldwide, its yield still faces significant challenges due to Fusarium wilt disease. This study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of *Trichoderma* isolated locally in Nigeria to control tomato wilting. *Trichoderma asperellum* (M23) was isolated from rhizosphere of a healthy maize plant in a local farm at Osun state, Nigeria. while the wilt pathogen, *Fusarium verticillioides* (Fv) used was isolated from an infected tomato plant. The fungi *Trichoderma* and *Fusarium* were characterized and documented in NCBI based on morphological and molecular methods, with accession numbers MN181574 and MN181570 respectively. Fv exhibited significant infestation in two tomato varieties UC82B and Ibadan local. However, the control group (untreated plants) and those treated with M23 showed no symptoms both in vitro and in vivo. Furthermore, Fv had negative effects on tomato growth, resulting in reduced plant height, stem girth, leaf number and leaf area. These matrices however, improved in plants that were co-inoculated with M23. Likewise, M23 exhibited significant growth stimulatory effects on the plants against the pathogen in terms of shoot, root and fruit biomass. This study therefore affirms the importance of *Trichoderma asperellum* both as a biocontrol agent against the wilting pathogen of tomatoes and growth- promoting agent.

Keywords: Tomatoes; rhizosphere; co-inoculated; biocontrol agent; growth promoting and growth

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Introduction

Tomatoes account for about 18% of total vegetables, consumed daily in Nigeria with an average of 50.6 g per one person. Nigeria is among the world's largest tomato producers; it was listed 16th in 2010 by the Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO 2010). Nigeria accounts for more than 541,800 Ha of soil for massive cultivation of tomatoes which happens to be the largest in Africa (FAO 2014). Nigeria increased her tomato production in 2010 which yielded over 1.8 million metric

tonnes and this alone was found to account for about 68.4 % of all tomatoes produced in West Africa (Singh et al. 2019).

Recently, the demand for tomatoes and its products surpassed their supply in Nigeria, thereby necessitating increased efforts in tomato production by combating impending problems of shortage. The high cost of some farming inputs and managements such as fertilizers and pesticide application, coupled with major challenges associated with pre- and post-

harvest disease management are major factors affecting tomato production in Nigeria (Okolo and Abubakar 2023; Torre et al. 2016). There are reports of enormous yield loss of tomatoes observed at the Guinea Savanna region in Nigeria, this was attributed to interference of fungal pathogens belonging to genera *Sclerotium*, *Colletotricum*, *Fusarium*, *Alternaria*, and *Pythium* (Olowe et al. 2021). It has also been established that major postharvest losses of tomato in Nigeria were as a result of fungal deterioration from these fungal pathogens (Okolo and Abubakar 2023).

Generally, the biocontrol strategy deals with the employment of living organisms and/or their products in controlling of diseases. It is environmentally friendly and generally believed to be less expensive as compared to using synthetic chemicals, mechanical machines, phototherapy or other means (Ma et al. 2023). Many *Trichoderma* species are popular biocontrol agents with enormous biocontrol potentials for managing several pathogens of plants. They have been reported to possess several mechanisms through which they inhibit plant pathogens, examples include their antagonistic or inhibitory effects through several mechanisms such as antibiosis (production of toxic metabolites), competition, and mycoparasitism (Pokhrel et al., 2022). Many *Trichoderma* species are now been packaged under many trade names for application against plant pathogens. The genus *Trichoderma* has been widely studied and the species are very promising as biocontrol agents, it is copious and available through the globe, can be found in most habitats and occurs in different types of soils (Molan 2009; Kacprzak et al. 2014).

Due to growing population, the Nigeria's consumption demands more than 2 to 3 million metric tons of tomatoes which significantly exceeds the current production level. As a developing economy, the country needs to explore feasible ways to enhance its tomato production capacity. This study aimed to identify potential biocontrol agents that can stimulate tomato growth and improve the ir defense mechanism against pathogens.

Materials and methods

Fungal Isolation

Fungi were isolated both from the rhizosphere soils and infected tomato plants using the growth medium, Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) prepared following the manufacturer's instructions. To source for *Trichoderma* species, thirty-six rhizosphere soil samples of 100 g each were collected with the aid of a soil auger from 25cm depth of plants growing in four different farms located in Osun state, in the tropical rainforest savanna regions of Nigeria. Since the study focused on isolating plant-beneficial biocontrol agents, rhizospheric soil samples were collected from a range of host plants, including pepper, eggplant, sugarcane, plantain, cassava, yam, maize, coconut, palm tree, okra and moringa plant. Serial dilution was used for the isolation of *Trichoderma* species. For the isolation of fungal pathogens, tomato samples showing symptoms of wilting were gathered from various farms, categorized into leaves and fruits, and appropriately labeled into sterile polyethylene bags and brought to the laboratory following the methods of Ajiboye and Sobowale (2022), Kumar et al. (2005) and Jonathan et al. (2012 & 2016). Fungal colony with characteristics green colour of *Trichoderma* species and white to pink colony with purple underside were selected for *Fusarium* species.

Pathogenicity test for the isolated fungi from infected tomatoes

Healthy tomato fruits were surface sterilized by rinsing with sterile distilled water alongside with cotton wool soaked in 70 % ethanol. Thereafter, 2mm diameter hole was made on the fruit using sterile disc corkborer. Furthermore, the corkborer was used to pick the mycelium of the pathogens at the actively growing mycelial tips, from a pure PDA culture and transferred into the hole bored in the healthy tomato. Control was set up by inoculating the fruits with sterile PDA at the same diameter disk. The hole was sealed thereafter with a molting candle wax. The ability of each of the pathogen to show symptoms in a healthy fruit similar to that on an infected tomato where it was initially isolated confirms its pathogenicity. Pathogen causing highest symptom was

selected and further characterized (Yang et al., 2024).

In-vitro antagonistic effect of Trichoderma against selected pathogen

The dual culture method on PDA medium was used for this test according to the procedures of Fahmi et al. (2012). All the isolated *Trichoderma* species were examined for their antagonistic effect against the selected pathogen by inoculating 5mm mycelia discs each of the *Trichoderma* species and the pathogen at opposite ends of 90 mm diameter PDA plates using the pairing method while control plate contains the pathogen only. The antagonistic activity was studied comparing the basal mycelia growth of both the pathogen and the *Trichoderma* species (Mohamed and Haggag 2006). Percentage inhibition of the pathogen was established by the formula;

$$\text{Percentage Inhibition (\%)} = \frac{R_1 - R_2}{R_1} \times 100$$

Where R₁= pathogen mycelia growth singly without co-inoculation of biocontrol agent (control), R₂ = pathogen radial growth (in dual culture).

The *Trichoderma* strain causing highest inhibition of the pathogen was selected and further characterized.

Molecular Identification of selected Trichoderma and pathogen

The procedures of Fan et al. (2023) were employed to carry out this work using the fungal ITS molecular characterization. This was performed by first extracting the genomic DNA from the fungal strains using the Zymogen super DNA kit. DNA quantity was measured using Nanodrop Spec (Agilent 2000 LT) while the quality of extracted DNA was checked by 1 % gel electrophoresis. Amplification of the ITS gene was performed on the 18S rRNA region (positions 1609-1627) and the 28S rRNA region (position 287-266) using a combination of ITS1 and ITS4 primers. according to the protocols of Al-Nasrawi (2012) and Asemoloye et al. (2017). Sequences generated for the pathogen and bioagent were subjected to BLAST search on the NCBI for identification.

Antagonistic effect of the selected Trichoderma species against the pathogen in-vivo

Before conducting the experiment, the soil to be used was first analyzed to physicochemical characteristics using the method of Sobowale and Ogunoye (2022) and Adewuyi and Olowu (2012). The in-vivo experiment was done in the greenhouse located at the Department of Plant Science and Biotechnology, FUYOYE, Nigeria. The soil was initially sieved with mesh to eliminate particles with a size greater than 1 mm. Then, four grams of the soil were measured and distributed into pots, which was arranged in a Factorial Completely Randomised Design (FCRD) within the greenhouse. The soils were potted and arranged with 25 cm spacing apart from each other, properly labeled based on the assigned treatment. Tomato varieties; UC82B and Ibadan local were used for this experiment, treated seeds (5) from each variety were planted into each pot in six replications, received a daily watering of 100 mL distilled water and then thinned to one after emergence.

To create spore suspensions for the pathogen and *Trichoderma*, their mycelium with spores (15 day old) was harvested into test tube mixed with sterile water and made into following concentrations (Gopalakrishnan et al. 2022; Senanayake, 2020):

- i) *Trichoderma* = 1.0 x 10⁵ spore/mL = Concentration 1 (C1)
- ii) *Trichoderma* = 1.0 x 10⁷ spore/mL = Concentration 2 (C2)
- iii) *Trichoderma* = 1.0 x 10⁹ spore/mL = Concentration 3 (C3)
- iv) Pathogen = 1.0 x 10⁵ spore/mL = Concentration 1 (C1)
- v) Pathogen = 1.0 x 10⁷ spore/mL = Concentration 2 (C2)

20mL of these concentrations were inoculated into the potted tomato plants of both varieties using a sterile syringe, the *Trichoderma* was inoculated into the soil 24 hours after the pathogen was inoculated. The experiment was prepared in different sets;

- i) plants treated with both pathogen and *Trichoderma*,
- ii) plants treated with only the pathogen (Fv₁),
- iii) plants treated with *Trichoderma* only (T1) and
- iv) plants having no fungi inoculation (controls denoted as NT).

Plant growth Analysis

Measurement of growth parameters for the tomato plants was done using the methods of Jonathan et al. (2012), the growth characteristics measured included the plant height, stem thickness, length of the petiole, the leaf number, and leaf area. The measurement data were collected over a twelve-week period, starting from two weeks after the initial planting. The calculation of the % growth change due to the pathogen interference was deduced following the methodology outlined by Jonathan et al. (2016) employing the formula:

$$\% \text{ Growth change} = \text{NT} - \text{Pa}/\text{NT}$$

Where the NT = untreated plant, Pa = pathogen inoculated plants (i.e., AsV₁, AsV₂, FvV₁ and FvV₂).

Biomass analysis was done by harvesting one plant from each of the different treatment groups after 12 weeks of planting and separated into root and shoot components, with roots representing the below-ground biomass and shoots

representing the above-ground biomass according to Jonathan et al. (2012).

Statistical Analysis

The data collected in this research were analyzed using Analysis of variance (ANOVA) through the GLM procedures of Statistical Analysis Software (SAS 9.6). To distinguish between means, the Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT) and the Least Significant Difference (LSD) were applied at a significant level of 0.05. Graphs were made using GraphPad Prism version 8.0.

Results

Selection of Trichoderma and Fusarium strains

This study employs the use of *Trichoderma* strain as biocontrol agents for fungal pathogen causing wilting, a common disease of tomatoes in Nigeria. To achieve this, fifty (50) *Trichoderma* strains were all isolated from different rhizosphere soil samples from plants located in different farms in Osun State, Nigeria (Table 1) and the most occurring strain M23 from the maize farmland with 40 % incidence was selected and characterized (Plate 1). Likewise, the *Fusarium* pathogens isolated from infected tomato plants were re-inoculated on healthy tomatoes using two tomato varieties (UC82B and Local Ibadan) from Nigeria. The most virulent pathogen causing disease in the inoculated plant strain Fv was selected (Plate 2).

Table 1: Occurrence of *Trichoderma* strains in plant rhizosphere across farms in Osun State, Nigeria.

Trichoderma Strain Code	Incidence in soil samples (N =50)	% Incidence	Plant Rhizosphere
M ₂₃ (T3)	20	40	Maize
Pr-1	7	14	Pepper
Cn-1	6	12	Coconut
Eg-1	5	10	Egg-plant
CS-1	3	6	Cassava
Sc-1	3	6	Sugar cane
TO-	3	6	Tomato
PL-1	2	4	Plantain
Tricho1	1	2	Banana

Plate 1: Morphological and microscopic (x40) view of the selected Bioagent agent *Trichoderma asperellum* strain M23.

Plate 2: Morphological and microscopic (x40) view of the selected pathogen, *Fusarium verticillioides* strain Old3.

The ITS amplification of the fungal gene for molecular characterization is presented in Table 2 below. The NCBI BLAST result using the fungal ITS-amplicon revealed their similarities with some other fungi which are already documented in the NCBI. It was observed that the BLAST search for bioagent strain M₂₃ had 99.01 % similarity matching with *Trichoderma asperellum* MK204287 while the *Fusarium* wilt pathogen strain Fv generated 99.63 % matching with *Fusarium verticillioides* MN181570 on the NCBI.

Table 2: NCBI BLAST results and Documented Accession numbers of Biocontrol agents and Pathogens used in this study.

Strain	Documented Accession No.	Identified Name	Accession Number of Best Blast Match	Blast search similarity (%)
M ₂₃ (T3)	MN181574	<i>Trichoderma asperellum</i>	MN181574	100.00
		<i>Trichoderma asperellum</i>	MK204287	99.01
		<i>Trichoderma asperellum</i>	KU059972	99.01
		<i>Trichoderma asperellum</i>	MK253265	99.01
Fv	MN181570	<i>Fusarium verticillioides</i>	MN181570	100.00
		<i>Fusarium verticillioides</i>	MF319906	99.63
		<i>Fusarium nygamai</i>	MH248271	97.58
		<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>	OR853713	97.59

Phylogeny and Relationships between the Isolated Bioagents and similar ones on the NCBI

The phylogenetic analysis comparing the *Trichoderma asperellum* and other isolated *Trichoderma* species with others previously documented in the NCBI database. The analysis revealed that these isolated strains exhibited notable similarities among themselves and had a shared ancestral lineage with similar strains in the NCBI. Specifically, Strain Sc-1 (MN181572) displayed a higher degree of similarity with

Trico (MN181573), while Strain Pr-1 (MN181575) exhibited greater resemblance to *Trichoderma* strain M₂₃ (MN181574), as illustrated in Figure 4.3. However, they exhibited molecular resemblances with *Trichoderma* Strain ksk3 (MK460812) listed on the NCBI, which act as parental traits for strain MH279746 (*T. viridiscens*), serving as the parent for strain KU942400 (*T. astroviride*), strain KP009338 (*T. viridiscens*), and subsequently for, strain KP009330 (*T. viridiscens*).

Figure 1: Phylogeny tree showing Relationships between the Isolated Bioagents and those on the NCBI

Phylogeny and Relationships between the Isolated Fusarium and similar ones on the NCBI

The phylogenetic investigation presented in Fig 2 showed that Fusarium wilt-causing pathogens isolated from tomatoes, exhibited significant resemblances among themselves and had a shared ancestral lineage with similar strains previously on

the NCBI database. For instance, *F. verticillioides* (MN181570) displayed a closer resemblance to *F. oxysporum* (MH607612), and together, they exhibited a high degree of similarity with *F. nygamy* (MH248271), *F. oxysporum* (MH569610), and *F. verticillioides* strain (MH248271) as shown in Fig. 4.3.

Figure 4.4: Phylogenetic Relationship among Isolated *Fusarium verticillioides* and *Alternaria solani* with other related strains already documented in NCBI

Antagonistic effect of Trichoderma on the wilt pathogen

The in-vitro antagonistic effect of the bioagent M23 was confirmed against the wilt pathogen of tomato using dual culture

experiment (Plate 2). It was observed that the bioagent exhibited clear inhibition of the pathogen *Fusarium verticillioides* strain Fv on dual culture.

Plate 3. Inhibitory Effect of bioagent *Trichoderma asperellum* (M₂₃) on tomato wilting pathogen *Fusarium verticillioides* (Fv). a = M₂₃ (T₃), b = Fv, c = both on dual culture.

The results obtained as presented in Tables 3 showed that the bioagents significantly stimulated the growth of both tomato varieties in varying levels and the tomato varieties had varying responses to the concentrations of applied bioagents. It was observed from the results in Tables 3 that *T. asperellum* (T₃) acted as a biostimulant as it significantly stimulated the growth of the tomato in varying degrees, (P≤0.05) at varying treatment

concentrations. Tomato variety UC82B had a significantly higher mean plant height of 24.19 and 19.03 cm observed for the T₃C₃ and FvC₂ + T₃C₃ respectively. These were followed by 17.46 cm recorded in combined treatment FvC₂ + T₃C₁ which is significantly higher than the untreated plant NT₁ 15.41 cm, while infected plants with pathogen alone (*F. verticillioides*) FvC₂ and FvC₁ had the least plant length of 9.94 and 10.34 cm

respectively. Also, the combined treatment FvC₁ + T₃C₃ and T₃C₂ had the highest leaf number of 8.72 and 8.69cm respectively and these were followed by treatments T₃C₃ and NT₂ which gave the leaf number of 8.22 and 8.28 respectively, while the pathogen treated plant FvC₂ and FvC₁ again had the least leaf number of 6.36 and 5.34 respectively. Furthermore, the results presented in Table 3 showed that the combined treatments FvC₁ + T₃C₂ had highest petiole length of 6.06, followed by NT₂ and T₃C₃ with petiole length of 2.78 and 2.59 cm while the pathogens FvC₁ again had the least petiole

length 1.59cm. The combined treatments T₃C₃ and T₃C₁ had the highest leaf area of 6.74 and 5.66 cm² while the pathogen treated plant FvC₂ and AsC₁ had the least leaf area of 4.27 and 3.55 cm² respectively. The highest stem girth of 0.39 and 0.37 were recorded for treatment T₃C₃ and FvC₁ + T₃C₁ respectively, followed by FvC₂ + T₃C₃ and NT₁ which had stem girth of 0.35 and 0.32 respectively while the pathogens treated plants AsC₂ had the least stem girth (0.23 cm).

Table 3: Antagonistic effects of *Trichoderma asperellum* M23 (Ag3) against *Fusarium verticillioides* causing wilting in tomato variety UC82B

Treatments	Plant Height (cm)	No of Leaf	Petiole Length (cm)	Leaf Area (cm ²)	Stem Girth (cm)
FvC ₁ + T ₃ C ₁	15.17 ^{bcd}	7.83 ^{ab}	2.37 ^{ab}	3.87 ^{bcd}	0.37 ^{ab}
FvC ₁ + T ₃ C ₂	11.15 ^{cde}	6.72 ^{abc}	6.06 ^a	2.38 ^d	0.25 ^{cd}
FvC ₁ + T ₃ C ₃	14.54 ^{bcd}	8.72 ^a	1.91 ^{ab}	3.89 ^{bcd}	0.28 ^{bcd}
FvC ₂ + T ₃ C ₁	17.46 ^{bc}	7.25 ^{ab}	2.57 ^{ab}	4.70 ^{bc}	0.32 ^{abc}
FvC ₂ + T ₃ C ₂	11.69 ^{cde}	6.25 ^{bc}	2.05 ^{ab}	3.42 ^{dc}	0.25 ^{cd}
FvC ₂ + T ₃ C ₃	19.03 ^b	7.89 ^{ab}	1.91 ^{ab}	4.22 ^{bcd}	0.35 ^{ab}
T ₃ C ₁	12.88 ^{cde}	6.92 ^{abc}	2.13 ^{ab}	5.66 ^{ab}	0.25 ^{cd}
T ₃ C ₂	16.57 ^{bcd}	8.69 ^a	2.06 ^{ab}	4.90 ^{abc}	0.33 ^{abc}
T ₃ C ₃	24.19 ^a	8.22 ^{ab}	2.59 ^{ab}	6.74 ^a	0.39 ^a
FvC ₁	10.36 ^e	5.34 ^c	1.59 ^b	4.27 ^{bcd}	0.25 ^{cd}
FvC ₂	9.94 ^e	6.36 ^{bc}	2.02 ^{ab}	3.55 ^{dc}	0.23 ^{cd}
NT ₁	15.41 ^{bcd}	8.28 ^{ab}	2.78 ^{ab}	4.58 ^{bc}	0.32 ^{abc}
Alpha	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05
Error DF	420	419	419	420	420
Err. Mean Squ.	117.92	16.31	59.87	14.25	0.03
LSD	5.03	1.83	0.88	1.97	0.08
F	5.18	2.51	0.82	3.15	4.2
Sig. level	<0.0001	0.0045	0.6176	0.0004	<0.0001

Values are means of three replicates, values across each column having the same superscript letters are not significantly different at (DMRT) at P≤0.05. C₁ = Treatment at 1.0 x 10⁵ spore/mL, C₂ = treatment at 1.0 x 10⁷ spore/mL, and C₃ = Treatment at 1.0 x 10⁹ spore/mL.

The results presented in Table 4 showed the antagonistic effects of *T. asperellum* strain M23 (T₃) against *F. verticillioides*, a pathogen causing wilting diseases in tomato variety (Ibadan local). Treatment FvC₂ + T₃C₃ gave the highest mean plant height of 26.46 cm, followed by FvC₂ + T₃C₁ and T₃C₂ which gave the plant height of 22.97cm and 22.66 cm respectively

while the infected plants with pathogen (*F. verticillioides*) alone FvC₂ had the least plant length of 4.54 cm. Also, T₃C₂ and T₃C₁ had the highest leaf number of 9.86 and 8.47 cm respectively. T₃C₃ and FvC₁ had mean number of leaf 7.97 and 7.78 respectively and these again were above the untreated plant NT₂ which had 7.58 while FvC₂ had the least leaf number of

2.32. It was also observed that treatments T₃C₂ and T₃C₁ had the highest petiole length of 2.68 and 2.60 cm respectively followed by FvC₁+T₃C₁ (2.58cm). This was higher than the the untreated control plants NT₂ with petiole length of 2.21 cm, while the pathogen infected plants FvC₂ had the least petiole length of 0.69 cm.

Likewise, the treatments T₃C₁ and T₃C₂ had the highest leaf area of 4.15 and 3.82 cm² with stem girth of 0.40 and 0.48 cm respectively and pathogen treated plants FvC₂ had the least leaf area (0.96 cm²) as well as the stem girth (0.12 cm).

Table 4: Antagonistic effects of *Trichoderma asperellum* M23 (Ag3) against *Fusarium verticillioides* causing wilting in tomato variety Ibadan Local

Treatments	Plant Height (cm)	No of Leaf	Petiole Length (cm)	Leaf Area (cm ²)	Stem Girth (cm)
FvC ₁ + T ₃ C ₁	19.30 ^{abcd}	7.42 ^b	2.58 ^a	1.91 ^{cdef}	0.35 ^{bc}
FvC ₁ + T ₃ C ₂	17.36 ^{bcd}	7.46 ^b	2.19 ^{ab}	2.37 ^{cde}	0.31 ^{bcd}
FvC ₁ + T ₃ C ₃	15.47 ^{dc}	6.86 ^b	2.01 ^{ab}	1.77 ^{def}	0.27 ^{cd}
FvC ₂ + T ₃ C ₁	22.97 ^{ab}	7.28 ^b	2.49 ^a	2.88 ^{bc}	0.38 ^b
FvC ₂ + T ₃ C ₂	21.16 ^{abc}	7.14 ^b	2.53 ^a	2.59 ^{cde}	0.34 ^{bc}
FvC ₂ + T ₃ C ₃	26.46 ^a	4.61 ^c	1.72 ^b	1.54 ^{ef}	0.24 ^d
T ₃ C ₁	21.98 ^{abc}	8.47 ^{ab}	2.60 ^a	4.15 ^a	0.40 ^b
T ₃ C ₂	22.66 ^{abc}	9.86 ^a	2.68 ^a	3.82 ^{ab}	0.48 ^a
T ₃ C ₃	21.53 ^{abc}	7.97 ^b	2.14 ^{ab}	1.82 ^{cdef}	0.34 ^{bc}
FvC ₁	13.21 ^a	7.78 ^b	1.95 ^{ab}	1.97 ^{cdef}	0.38 ^b
FvC ₂	4.54 ^e	2.32 ^d	0.69 ^c	0.96 ^f	0.12 ^e
NT ₂	13.02 ^a	7.58 ^b	2.21 ^{ab}	2.80 ^{cd}	0.34 ^{bc}
Alpha	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05
Error DF	418	418	418	420	420
Err. Mean Squ.	189.11	12.96	1.61	4.21	0.03
LSD	5.34	1.91	0.76	0.95	0.08
F	6.61	9.94	6.48	7.38	10.45
Sig. level	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001

Values are means of three replicates, values across each column having the same superscript letters are not significantly different at (DMRT) at P≤0.05. C₁ = Treatment at 1.0 x 10⁵ sporeml⁻¹, C₂ = treatment at 1.0 x 10⁷ sporeml⁻¹, and C₃ = Treatment at 1.0 x 10⁹ sporeml⁻¹.

Biostimulatory effect of the isolated Trichoderma strain on tomato roots against wilting pathogen

The stimulatory effects of isolated *Trichoderma* strain M₂₃ (T₃) were studied on the biomass of two tomato varieties (UC82B and Ibadan local) at different concentrations. As presented in Plate 4, the bioagent significantly enhanced the root proliferation against the wilting pathogen.

It was observed that the Pathogen attacks the roots making the plant grow wilted and stunted while this effect became reduced or removed when the bioagent was co-inoculated with the pathogen. In addition, the bioagent treated plant shows enhanced root proliferation even above the control (plant with no fungal treatment).

UC82B

Ibadan local

Plate 4. Stimulatory effect of *Trichoderma asperellum* on the root proliferation of tomato varieties. a = No-treatment plant, b = plant with *Trichoderma* and pathogen both at 1.0×10^5 spore L^{-1} , c = plant with *Trichoderma* alone at 1.0×10^5 spore L^{-1} and d = plants with pathogen alone at 1.0×10^5 spore L^{-1} .

Biostimulatory effect of the isolated Trichoderma strain on tomato biomass against wilting pathogen

The stimulatory effects of bioagent *T. asperellum* M₂₃ (T₃) on the wilt pathogen (*F. verticillioides*) as observed in the weight of variety UC82B as well Ibadan local is presented in Fig. 1 and Fig. 4 respectively. It was observed as presented in Fig. 1 that *T. asperellum* (T₃) enhanced tomato variety UC82B against the wilting pathogen as the highest Shoot Field Weight (SFW) of 6.01 and 4.18 g were observed in treatments with T₃C₁ and FvC₁ + T₃C₁ respectively followed by treatments T₃C₃ (4.00g) and T₃C₂ (3.20g). These were greater than those observed in untreated variety NT₁ (2.42g) while the plants treated with the pathogen alone (*F. verticillioides*)

FvC₁ (0.15g) and FvC₂ (0.05g) had the least SFW. Also, combined treatments T₃C₂ and FvC₂ + T₃C₂ had the best Shoot Dried Weight (SDW) value of 1.35 and 1.17g respectively, while the T₃C₁ (0.09g) had the least SDW. Likewise, Fig. 1 showed that the treatments T₃C₁ and FvC₁ + T₃C₃ gave the best Root Field Weight (RFW) of 4.50g and 4.00g respectively, while the pathogen treated plants FvC₁ (0.12g) and FvC₂ (0.28g) gave the lowest RFW. The combined treatments FvC₂ + T₃C₂ (1.00g) and single treatment T₃C₂ (0.80g) produce the best RDW followed by FvC₁ + T₃C₁ (0.72g). These were greater than the untreated variety NT₁ (0.06g) while the pathogen treated plants FvC₂ (0.02g) again had the lowest RDW.

Figure 1. Effect of *Fusarium verticillioides* on Biomass of UC82B as mediated by *Trichoderma asperellum* (M₂₃).

In addition, the *T. asperellum* (T₃) improved the tomato variety (Ibadan local) against the inoculated wilting pathogen (*F. verticillioides*). As presented in Fig. 2, the best Shoot Field Weight (SFW) was recorded in combined treatments FvC₂ + T₃C₃ (6.00g) and T₃C₂ (5.70g) followed by treatments FvC₁ + T₃C₃ (5.40g) and FvC₂ + T₃C₁ (5.14g). These were higher than untreated plant NT₂ while the plants treated with the pathogen alone (*F. verticillioides*) FvC₁ (1.21cm) had the least SFW. Also, the combined treatments FvC₂ + T₃C₃ and FvC₂ + T₃C₁ had the best SDW

of 3.10 and 2.30g respectively, while the pathogen treated plants FvC₂ (0.30g) gave the lowest SDW. Again, it was observed that the combined treatments FvC₁ + T₃C₃ and FvC₂ + T₃C₁ gave the best RFW of 4.80 and 3.82g respectively, and these were greater than those of the untreated variety NT₁ (1.5g) while the pathogen treated plants FvC₁ (0.81g) had the least. The combined treatment FvC₁ + T₃C₂ (2.34g) had the best RDW while the pathogen treated plants FvC₁ (0.10g) and FvC₂ (0.23g) gave the least.

Figure 2. Effect of *Fusarium verticillioides* on Biomass of Ibadan local as mediated by *Trichoderma asperellum* (M_{23}).

Biostimulatory effect of the isolated Trichoderma strain on tomato fruits (yielding) against wilting pathogen

The isolated bioagent *Trichoderma asperellum* M_{23} (T_3) was shown to exert significant stimulatory effects on the two varieties (UC82B and Ibadan local) against different concentrations of *Fusarium verticillioides* (FvC₁ and FvC₂) as presented in Tables 5. It was observed that *T. asperellum* (T_3) improved the fruit yield of both varieties against the inoculated pathogen (*F. verticillioides*). For tomato variety UC82B, the treatments T_3C_2 (18.77g) had the highest fruit weight followed by FvC₁ + T_3C_2 and T_3C_1 with (16.78g) which is bigger than those

recorded for FvC₂ + T_3C_2 (16.70g) and T_3C_3 (16.70g) when compared with Non Treated Plant NT (13.56g) while the pathogens treated plants FvC₂, and FvC₁ had the least fruit weight of (4.77g) and (9.44g) respectively. Likewise, it was observed that tomato variety Ibadan local with the best fruit weight was T_3C_2 (16.78g) and FvC₂ + T_3C_2 (16.77g) followed by treatments FvC₂ + T_3C_3 (15.73g) and FvC₂+ T_3C_1 (15.66g) when compared with NT (13.44g) while the pathogens treated plants FvC₂ and FvC₁ had the least fruit weight of (8.45g) and (9.66g) respectively.

Table 5: Effects of Biocontrol agent *Trichoderma asperellum* (M₂₃) on Fruit weight of Tomato varieties

Treatments	N	UC82B (g)	Ibadan local (g)
FvC ₁ + T ₃ C ₁	60	9.78 ^c	15.39 ^{bc}
FvC ₁ + T ₃ C ₂	60	16.78 ^{ab}	15.55 ^{bc}
FvC ₁ + T ₃ C ₃	60	15.76 ^{ab}	15.05 ^{bcd}
FvC ₂ + T ₃ C ₁	60	8.89 ^{cd}	15.66 ^{bc}
FvC ₂ + T ₃ C ₂	60	16.70 ^{ab}	16.77 ^b
FvC ₂ + T ₃ C ₃	60	15.00 ^b	15.73 ^{bc}
T ₃ C ₁	60	16.78 ^{ab}	14.56 ^{cd}
T ₃ C ₂	60	18.77 ^a	16.78 ^b
T ₃ C ₃	60	16.30 ^{de}	15.62 ^{bc}
FvC ₁	60	9.44 ^c	9.66 ^e
FvC ₂	60	4.77 ^e	8.45 ^e
NT	60	13.56 ^b	13.44 ^d
A		0.05	0.05
Err. DF		40	40
Err. Mean Squ.		3.39	0.87
LSD		3.04	1.54
F Value		14.42	34.00
Sig		<0.0001	<0.0001

Values are means of three replicates, values across each column having the same superscript letters are not significantly different at (DMRT) at $P \leq 0.05$. C₁ = Treatment at 1.0×10^5 spore/mL⁻¹, C₂ = treatment at 1.0×10^7 spore/mL⁻¹, and C₃ = Treatment at 1.0×10^9 spore/mL⁻¹.

Discussion

This research demonstrated how the selected *Trichoderma* act as biostimulatory agent (bioagent) to reduce the damaging influence of wilt (*Fusarium verticillioides*) pathogen of tomatoes using the two varieties of tomatoes (UC82B and Ibadan local). The impact of *Fusarium verticillioides* was notable on both tomato varieties, as evidenced in this research. This study aligns with the reports of Ganie et al. (2018), Maurya et al. (2019), El-Sheekh et al. (2019) and Attia et al. (2022), which established the detrimental effects of the pathogen. These studies have reported that this pathogenic fungus is capable of inducing wilting disease in tomato plants, consequently diminishing their ability to produce higher yields. Biocontrol, which was first investigated in the mid-1920s, has gained substantial attention in recent years from scientists, industries, and scholarly researchers. This

trend is evident from the works of Kuhn and Neumann (2017) and Adnan et al. (2019). *Trichoderma* species constitute one among the major and extensive fungi groups that have been studied as biocontrol agents. In a very similar study, Cotxarrera et al. (2012) reported the use of sewage sludge compost mixed with *Trichoderma asperellum* spores to reduce *Fusarium* wilt of tomato. Concerning research centered around *Trichoderma* species as a solution for managing plant diseases, 90% of investigations have involved the utilization of various strains of *Trichoderma* (Guzmán-Guzmán et al. 2023a&b). *Trichoderma* strains are indeed capable, with various numerous results supporting their potentials, to inhibit plant pathogens using several mechanisms ranging from mycoparasitism, competition, antibiosis (production of toxic metabolites), and enzyme degradation of pathogens cell wall (Harman et al. 2004). Recent researches according to Thangaraj et al.

(2025), Sheoran et al. (2025) and Aravindharajan et al. (2024) reported that many *Trichoderma asperellum* strains can stimulate resistance effect in plants and as well enhance their growths. This they do by either modifying the soil physical and chemical conditions or by root colonization and insight the systemic acquired resistance in the host cell. Prachi et al. (2019) observed a significant suppression of Fusarium wilt disease by *T. asperellum*. Many other works have affirmed the biological control activities of these bioagents on various plant pathogens (Akrami and Yousefi 2015; Lakshman et al. 2016; Andleeb et al. 2017; Mwangi et al. 2019).

In this study, the growth stimulation by *T. asperellum* was evident as the treated tomato plants exhibited superior attributes such as increased plant height, leaf number, petiole length, stem girth, leaf area, and fruit yield compared to untreated plants (controls). This finding aligns with previous studies demonstrating the growth-enhancing effects of Trichoderma. Notably, a recent report by Kumar et al. (2024) also supported the role of Trichoderma in promoting plant growth. Due to its ability to manage plant diseases, numerous commercial products have been formulated utilising various *Trichoderma* species. Furthermore, successful outcomes were demonstrated by Singh et al. (2013), showcasing that the leaf treatment or inoculation with strains of *T. viride* and *T. harzianum* can effectively control *Alternaria porri* and increased the inhibition of yield-reducing purple blotch disease in onions. Our results also align with the conclusions drawn by Sobowale et al. (2007), Sobowale (2019) and Kumar et al. (2024) all of which emphasized the reliability and efficacy of using Trichoderma biocontrol agents against pathogens that are more aggressive and virulent.

Conclusion

The pathogenicity of *Fusarium verticillioides* (fungus causing wilting) of tomatoes were affirmed in this study on two varieties, UC82B and Ibadan local. Results obtained affirm that the action of this pathogen significantly affected the tomatoes but vary by the concentration of their inoculum in soil. The pathogen at

concentration of 1.0×10^5 spore L^{-1} exerted highest effects on tomato variety UC82B while on tomato variety Ibadan local at concentration of 1.0×10^7 spore L^{-1} . In addition, it was established in this study that soil treatments using the isolated *Trichoderma asperellum* strain M23 posed significantly inhibitory effects on the pathogen on dual culture using PDA medium. It was also established that the bioagent, M23 enhanced the tomato plant growth and yielding against the effects of Fusarium wilt pathogen co-inoculated on the two tomato varieties. The inoculation of the *Trichoderma* in the soil 24 hours even after the pathogen has been established in the soil shows considerable antagonistic effect against both pathogens. These actions of bioagent M23 were also confirmed to be affected by the concentration of their inoculum in soils as they exerted higher inhibitory and antagonistic effects on the pathogens at 1.0×10^9 spore L^{-1} in the soil. These effects also reflected on harvest biomass of shoot and roots as well as the fruit yields of the tomatoes.

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